

**Coherent & Cross-compliant Ocean Governance for
Delivering the EU Green Deal for European Seas**

Case Study: Mediterranean Sea

Case Study Report – V2

Deliverable version	V2
Date	22.3.2024
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PART 1: Setting the scene

1.1 Summary of the case study

The Mediterranean sea presents the second largest biodiversity hotspot in the world. The region is highly fragmented (politically, culturally, demographically, and socio-economically), with a pronounced north-south divide. The northern countries tend to be economically rich, EU member states or candidate countries, while southern and eastern states are significantly poorer, with growing populations (CEPF, 2017). The marine policy landscape of the Mediterranean is complex, due to the interplay between the EU, Mediterranean level, and international policies, which bring with them a wide variety of different actors.

This case study aims to study the implementation of the Green Deal marine policies, with a focus on biodiversity and climate change integration in the fishery policies, and the challenges of cross-compliance across the Mediterranean sea basin area. However, Mediterranean sea is shared between 22 coastal states, only eight of them part of the EU (with addition of Monaco, with close EU ties, and four EU candidate states). Consequently, the European Green Deal is only directly relevant for the minority of the Mediterranean countries and the scope of the case study needs to be broadened.

United Nations Environment Programme/Mediterranean Action Plan (UNEP/MAP) and Plan Bleu (2020) identify eight major threats to the Mediterranean environment and development, with fisheries being one of them. General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean (GFCM) assessments show that 73% of assessed fish stocks in the Mediterranean are overfished, with only about 50% of all stocks being assessed. This is a decrease from 88% in 2014. Additionally, 18% of catches are discarded (depends considerably on the type of fishing gear used).

Moreover, climate change is further exacerbating the situation, as the basin is warming and acidifying faster than the global average, forcing movements of fish species and a high rate of biological invasions. Economic activities in the region, including fisheries, are inextricably linked to the climatic and environmental conditions. While there is a long history of highly diverse fisheries, contributing to economy, health, and wellbeing in Mediterranean nations, those are now threatened. The influence of climate change on fisheries is complex, but since most Mediterranean fish stocks are overexploited, the whole sector is more vulnerable to further pressures.

At the same time, changing environmental conditions are also affecting rich biodiversity, as the warmer waters have already led to mass mortality events in coralligenous habitats, sponges, and among molluscs, while seagrass meadows are also regressing. The degradations of seagrasses and coralligenous assemblages can both be, at least partly, linked also to fishing practices (UNEP/MAP and Plan Bleu, 2020). While almost 10% of the Mediterranean is formally protected in MPAs, only about 10% of them are considered to be appropriately managed, and only about 0.06% of Mediterranean Sea enjoys strict protection.

The environmental and anthropogenic pressures on the Mediterranean, as a whole, are doubtless even more complex. However, even this comparatively narrow focus on only three policy areas, already demonstrates daunting complexity of challenges on both environmental and policy sides.

1.2 Specific research questions

1) How are biodiversity and climate change currently integrated in fisheries management - on paper and in practice?

- a) We will look at strategies and the interplay among policies and plans at the level of the entire Mediterranean and how different elements of governance, science-policy-society interfaces, funding, and others influence their implementation.

2) What are differences in this integration between different scales?

- a) We will investigate this current state of affairs in integration at different scales, identifying levels where integration seems to be more successful (and why) as well as constraints imposed by one level to the other, or opportunities seized at one level that bring a better integration of biodiversity and climate change into fisheries management. We will in particular look at the Mediterranean region (GFCM and alike).

3) Which options and solutions would help strengthening the integration?

1.3 Policy focus

In this case study we focus on the intersection of biodiversity, climate change, and fisheries. The Mediterranean EU Member States are bound by the same policies as the rest of the EU. Within these three specific fields, the most relevant policies are the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), Habitats and Birds Directives (HBD), as well as policies stemming directly from the European Green Deal, such as the European Climate Law, Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and the Nature Restoration Law. Apart from the eight Mediterranean EU Member States (Spain, France, Italy, Slovenia, Croatia, Greece, Cyprus), additional four states are progressively aligning their legal systems with EU legislation through their accession procedures, (Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Albania, Türkiye), although they are at very different stages of accession and alignment with the EU.

The remaining 10 states (Syria, Lebanon, Israel, State of Palestine, Egypt, Libya, Tunisia, Algeria, Morocco) are not bound by the EU legislation, nor the objectives of the Green Deal, apart from where the Green Deal is aligned with other global agreements. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this wider policy context. The overall environmental policy umbrella in the Mediterranean is provided through the Barcelona Convention, which is administered through the Secretariat of UNEP/MAP and through its Regional Activity Centres. On paper, Barcelona Convention's approach to management of the marine environmental status is broadly aligned with the EU' MSFD, although the extent of this integration should be more closely researched.

While Barcelona Convention officially covers also fisheries, in effect the Mediterranean fisheries are actually managed through the relevant Regional Fisheries Management Organisations, of which two are active in the Mediterranean. The main and the most overarching one is the General Fisheries Commission for the Mediterranean and Black Seas (GFCM), which operates underneath the United Nations' Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO). The second RFMO is International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas (ICCAT) which manages tunas and tuna-like species throughout the Atlantic, Mediterranean and Black Seas.

At this moment, there is no separate institutional or policy framework in place specifically for climate change. The sectoral policies are in the process of integrating climate change

considerations and a new climate change related Regional Activity Centre under Barcelona Convention is being established.

A variety of other global international agreements also bind the Mediterranean states, such as Convention on Biodiversity, Bern Convention, Ramsar Convention, United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, among others. However, these are mainly implemented through the regional policies, so some of their overarching goals (such as 30:30 or the 1.5/2°C warming) will be investigated through regional policies. These different policy areas are aiming for coherence and cross-sectoral integration in their texts, further supported through a number of institutions, such as the Union for the Mediterranean (UfM), WWF Mediterranean, the Mediterranean Conservation Society, and the Blue World Institute of Marine Research and Conservation facilitate cooperation among Mediterranean countries on environmental protection and biodiversity conservation.

1.4 Institutions and stakeholders involved in data collection activities

A screening of relevant institutions, policies, and initiatives was performed through literature review and first exploratory contacts established in that way. This same process was also followed to identify the main sources of information and existing processes. Table 1 summarises the main stakeholders to be contacted and their publications examined for the purposes of this case study. In order to keep the number of documents manageable, the main sources of documents will be restricted to GFCM Strategies and Decisions, biodiversity and climate change relevant reports and actions of the Barcelona Convention, and comparisons of legal texts between the EU, ICCAT, GFCM, and Barcelona Convention. This way all three main policy areas and their processes are covered:

- Fisheries – GFCM, ICCAT, EU – CFP, MSFD, Barcelona Convention – SPA/BD, IMAP
- Biodiversity – EU - BDS, HBD, MSFD, Barcelona Convention – SPA/BD, IMAP, interactions with GFCM
- Climate change – diffused in the above mentioned processes

The main data sources for this study will thus be documents from the processes mentioned above, observations and knowledge from interviews with key stakeholders, and ethnographic approaches during the relevant meetings (such as the Fish Forum).

Table 1: Main stakeholder institutions in the Mediterranean on the topics of fisheries, biodiversity, and climate change

Stakeholder	Type of the institution	Framework
UNEP-MAP (Secretariat of the Barcelona Convention)	Regional Sea Convention (RSC)	Barcelona Convention administers a system of policies and monitoring requirements similar to MSFD, ICZM Protocol and in future also on climate change and MSP
PAP/RAC (Priority Action Programme)	Regional Activity Centre (RAC) under RSC	MSP/ICZM and MSFD between non-EU and EU member states (project based)
Plan Bleu	Regional Activity Centre (RAC) under RSC	Environment and Sustainable Development Observatory, home of Mediterranean climate change assessment (MedECC)
SPA/RAC (Special Protected Area)	Regional Activity Centre (RAC) under RSC	Conservation and fisheries (including non-native and invasive species) policies under the Barcelona Convention

FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation)	UN Agency	Fisheries and aquaculture
GFCM (General Fisheries Commission for Mediterranean and Black Seas)	Regional Fisheries management Organisation (RMFO)	Fisheries RFMO for Mediterranean and Black Seas
ICCAT (International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas)	RMFO	Fisheries focus on large pelagics (tunas and tuna-like species)
CBD Secretariat (Convention on Biological Diversity)	International convention	Convention covering conservation of biodiversity and the new Global Biodiversity Framework
IOC UNESCO (Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission)	UNESCO body	Promoting international cooperation and coordinating programmes in research, services and capacity building
IMO (International Maritime Organization)	UN specialised agency	Safety and security of shipping and prevention of marine and atmospheric pollution by ships
MedPAN (Mediterranean network of Marine Protected Areas Managers)	MPA managers network	MPAs
UfM (Union for the Mediterranean)	Intergovernmental organisation	Regional cooperation (rather political – capacity building and Blue economy)
LIFE (Low Impact Fishers of Europe)	Platform of organisations	Interest platform representing small scale fishers across all European sea basins
MEDAC (Mediterranean Advisory Council)	Non-profit organisation (fishery sector)	Fisheries (under the CFP framework)
MOI-ECSDE (Mediterranean Information Office for the Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development)	Non-profit federation of Mediterranean NGOs	Environment and development
IUCN Med (International Union for Conservation of Nature)	Intergovernmental institutions	biodiversity
WWF MedPo (World Wildlife Fund)	NGO	Biodiversity

Mediterranean Programme Office)		
OCEANA	NGO	Biodiversity
ACCOBAMS (Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean and Contiguous Atlantic Area)	International convention	biodiversity
DG MARE (Directorate-General of the European Commission for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries)	European Commission	Fisheries, CFP, MSP
DG ENV (Directorate-General of the European Commission for Environment)	European Commission	MSFD, HBD, BDS, Green Deal
JRC (Directorate-General of the European Commission – Joint Research Centre)	European Commission	Scientific support for European Commission
EP PECH (European Parliament's Committee on Fisheries)	European Parliament	fisheries
EP ENVI (European Parliament's Committee on Environment, Public Health and Food Safety)	European Parliament	environment
EUSAIR (EU Strategy for the Adriatic-Ionian Region)	EU macro-regional strategy	Sustainable tourism, environmental quality, connecting the region, blue growth
ISPRA Ambiente	National institute for environmental protection and research - Italy	Biodiversity, environment, MSFD, CFP, WFD, HBD, BDS
University of Ancona	Academia - Italy	Biodiversity, fisheries
CNRS (Centre national de la	Research - France	Biodiversity, environment, fisheries

recherche scientifique)		
University of Aegean	Academia Greece	- Environment, fisheries, MSP, MSFD
SZN (Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn)	Research - Italy	Biodiversity

1.5 Data collection activities

This case study will be based around document analysis (desk-based study), semi-structured interviews, and ethnography.

1.5.1 Document analysis

The document analysis will cover the above mentioned main processes and institutions from the EU and Mediterranean level policies covering fisheries, biodiversity, and climate change. The document analysis will focus on one hand on extraction of mentions of harmonisation of different policies together and on the other hand on comparisons between the coverage and approach to the same issues within different policy sets. This will focus in particular around:

- Biodiversity
 - Comparisons of the Barcelona Convention's IMAP system with MSFD
 - Comparison of biodiversity coverage of HBD with Barcelona Convention's SPA/BD Protocol
- Fisheries
 - Comparisons of decisions between CFP, GFCM, and ICCAT
- General integration
 - Comparison of Barcelona Conventions post-2020 SAP BIO (Strategic Action Plan for Biodiversity) with GFCM Strategy for 2030 with EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030

1.5.2 Semi-structured interviews

Since the great scope of the case study prevents meaningful detailed study of the implementation of the above mentioned policies, while the interplays between different policies from different governance systems (EU, FAO, Barcelona Convention) are complex, the document analysis will be supplemented with semi-structured interviews. These interviews will first focus on the institutional representatives of the main policy actors in the Mediterranean (GFCM, FAO, Barcelona Convention, EU, ICCAT), before extending also to the broader group, including NGOs, academia, and various international platforms, which hold crucial insights into the functioning of the policies and their effect on the ground.

1.5.3 Ethnography

Ethnographic observations during key events in the region will be employed to further complement the document analysis and semi-structured interviews, particularly by providing insights into relationships between different institutions and to the extent different kinds of knowledge are used to support different decisions or approaches. This is primarily going to be used during the Fish Forum, but if other relevant events will be identified, they will also be targeted.

1.5.4 Focussed case studies

In order to assess how the Mediterranean level policies are used (or not) in national, regional, and local level implementation, collaborations will be established with the CrossGov French Mediterranean case study and PERMAGOV project Italian case study (Torre Guaceto MPA with sustainable fisheries). Additionally, local workshops (French Mediterranean Marseille workshop – April 2024) and stakeholder meetings (CrossGov consortium meeting – Marseille, June 2024) will be used to see which considerations from international level are taken into account in on the ground implementation.

1.6 Risks associated to this case study approach.

Three main risks have been identified to carry the case study:

- The tight time frame (February 2024 - May 2024)
- Great geographical and cultural scope (22 countries, 12 languages, different development stages)
- Extended policy scope beyond the European Green Deal and complex policy interplays

As already indicated in the preceding sections, these risks will be mainly addressed by constricting the scope of the study to the international policy level and their coherence and cross-compliance on paper, while the implementation patters will be inferred from interviews, but not studied in detail on national or sub-national levels. Additionally, the possible collaborations with other case studies will be maximised to provide some detail on implementation of those policies in lieu of conducting detailed investigations within the Mediterranean case study.